

**D.3.2.1. Review of
surveillance activities carried
out by member countries**
JIP COVRIN WP3

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REVIEW OF SURVEILLANCE ACTIVITIES CARRIED OUT BY MEMBER COUNTRIES

1. Introduction

COVRIN is a joint integrative project within the European Joint Program for One Health project (OHEJP) that aims to first, identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV-2 and second, to generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV-2. Through these objectives, the project aims to develop common Covid-19 protocols that support the OHEJP collaborations, and to develop a common infrastructure to foresee Covid-19 research. COVRIN deliverables will then be integrated into the work of OHEJP partners to reduce the overlaps in Covid-19 research.

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19), which is caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), was first identified in December 2019 in Wuhan, China, and has since spread rapidly, evolving into a full-blown pandemic. This JIP aims to integrate coronavirus research activities of all OHEJP partners. The project will have two main operational objectives: The first one will be to identify the drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV-2. The second one will be to generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV-2. Within the overall EJP One Health strategic goals, the overall aim of the COVRIN project will be to generate and share data of integrative research activities on virus-host interactions, virus evolution and drivers for emergence, risk assessment and risk modelling, in order to increase the preparedness for future Coronavirus outbreaks. Besides a work package on coordination and communication, including activities to connect with stakeholders and avoid overlaps with other projects, the project will have four integrative research work packages.

Divided into four work packages, work package 3 (WP3) aims to integrate the surveillance activities, map surveillance data, and identify risk factors for virus transmission in wildlife, food producing animals, pets and the environment (including sewage). To establish models for transmission routes and risk assessment in a One Health perspective.

2. Description of the task

Aligned surveillance will be combined with the data on bioavailability in samples (WP1) to inform risk assessment and transmission models. The outcomes of WP3 will therefore provide evidence for decision makers and other stakeholders to understand the risk posed by potential animal hosts, the environment, or fomites in the transmission of SARS-CoV-2.

Specifically, task 3.2 seeks to provide an evaluation of current surveillance activities being carried out, particularly in the animal sector, and assessment of similarities and differences between member countries, as well as opportunities for alignment.

3. Preliminary Work focused on UK surveillance activities

To begin with, the study period and the scope of the data were defined. For the study period, data on surveillance activities were collected for the period prior to the start of the pandemic, that is prior to March 2020, and extended beyond that of March 2020 to capture those surveillance activities still in operation. The scope of the surveillance activity data was such that data for SARS-CoV-2 in animals was restricted to terminology associated with pets, livestock, and wildlife (Appendix A). To collect these data, engagement with all partners was needed. Therefore, to better frame the questions and requests to the consortium, preliminary work was initiated with a focus on surveillance activities in one country, the UK. This was chosen because the Animal Plant Health Agency (APHA) in the UK is a strong and active partner in COVRIN. This initial search included both historical and current surveillance activities, available in the public domain and being conducted by, or in collaboration with APHA across the United Kingdom.

APHA is an executive agency of the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA), and was identified as the organisation most likely to be conducting surveillance on SARS-CoV-2 in pets, livestock, and wildlife. APHA was recently made the reference laboratory for SARS-CoV-2, however primary diagnosis of the virus is completed by an external provider; IDEXX Laboratories. APHA is the confirmatory body in which they re-sample and performs in-house diagnostics, before reporting positive results to World Animal Health Organisation (OIE), as although not a notifiable disease in the UK, SARS-CoV-2 is a reportable disease to the OIE. An official APHA mandate is available, which details the case definitions, testing and international reporting obligations of SARS-CoV-2 to APHA in GB, and the Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs (DEFRA) in Northern Ireland, as the relevant competent authorities. It also outlines the UK's international reporting obligations to the OIE.

3.1 Preliminary Results for UK surveillance activities

Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)

The APHA works collaboratively with The Bat Conservation Trust, via passive surveillance. This is a DEFRA funded lyssavirus surveillance programme and is not SARS-CoV-2 specific. The objective of this collaboration is to monitor for *lyssavirus*, with targeted testing currently completed in specific species of bats (pipistrelles, greater and lesser horseshoes, Bechstein's, barbastelles and grey long-eared bats) via the collection of dead bat samples from the public, and bat dropping collections. The public can contact APHA with a dead bat samples if found and are advised to keep the specimen in a cool area prior to the arrival of the collection package sent by APHA. Guidance is provided by APHA to the general public on the handling of specimens. The public are advised to place the samples in the tube provided by APHA, seal and wrap in absorbent material, and a submission form is to be completed before placing in a freepost envelope provided by APHA. A screening of bats in households that have tested positive for SARS-COV2 is also ongoing, especially where bat roosts have been identified as being within close proximity (The Bat Conservation Trust, 2021). This work is ongoing with amendments being continually applied at a policy level due to restrictions in place by Natural England, which prevent persons from entering roosts of bats due to biosafety concerns. Because of this limitation, faecal samples are collected instead rather than samples from live bats.

Further, sampling activities specific for wildlife sample collection at the APHA currently include samples from badgers, squirrels, deer, smaller carnivores (eg. minks), rodents, and horseshoe bats. Types of sampling collected, include nasal and oropharyngeal swabs. Blood serum and tissues samples from road traffic accident specimens in badgers, are also collected in collaboration with Nottingham University with an emphasis on Tuberculosis detection. There are also ongoing collaborative projects with Oxford University's Wildlife Conservation Research unit who are conducting research with a focus on mink. There are also plans to integrate more surveillance on existing sampling programmes.

We identified a research group based at Liverpool university called Small Animal Veterinary Surveillance Network (SAVSNET) and here they are conducting small animal covid surveillance, particularly acute vomiting associated with the disease in dogs (Collins et al., 2021).

Governmental Organisations

Briefing notes released by APHA act as the main communicative document delivering advice for veterinary and veterinary laboratory professionals. Species specific briefing notes are compiled by the APHA Wildlife Expert group, and produced by the partnership comprising of, APHA, Scotland's Rural College (SRUC) Veterinary Services, Institute of Zoology (IoZ), the Centre for Environment, Fisheries and Aquaculture (Cefas), the Wildfowl and Wetlands Trust (WWT), Natural England (NE), Forestry England (FE) and the Garden Wildlife Health (GWH).

Additionally, quarterly reports are published by the Great Britain Wildlife Disease Surveillance Partnership on the monitoring, and identification of trends in disease specifically for wildlife species. The documents provide a summary of disease surveillance of wildlife and cover notifiable disease, zoonotic disease, emerging and endemic diseases, UK priority and conservation concern species.

The Human Animal Infections and Risk Surveillance Group (HAIRS), a multi-agency horizon scanning and risk assessment group, acts as a forum to identify and discuss infections with potential for interspecies (pets, livestock, and wildlife) transfer. In particular, this group has published a qualitative assessment on the risk that SARS-CoV-2 infection in UK in the Mustelidae population (captive ferrets and mink populations) presents to the UK human population and is available in the public domain (<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/hairs-risk-assessment-on-sars-cov-2-in-mustelinae-population>)

The Horizon Scanning Programme is steered by the Cabinet Secretary's Advisory Group. The programme focuses on developing networks, bringing emerging issues to a senior-level audience, as well as commissioning work on areas of interest. The Scanning Surveillance Network is overseen by UK Surveillance Forum (UKSF) including the chief veterinary officer, and is a partnership between APHA, APHA's partner post-mortem providers, livestock keepers, vet surgeons and stakeholders.

A summary of the different organisations involved in SARS-CoV-2 surveillance in the UK is shown in the table below.

Table 1. Preliminary search results generated via terminology outlined in Appendix A.

Non-Governmental Organisation (NGO's)	Governmental Organisations
Bat Conservation Trust	The Horizon Scanning Programme
Small Animal Veterinary Surveillance Network (SAVSNET)	Scanning Surveillance Network
	UK Surveillance Forum (UKSF)
	Human Animal Infections and Risk Surveillance Group (HAIRS)
	APHA Briefing Note
	The wildlife Species Expert Group (SEG)

3.2 Discussion for UK surveillance activities

We found that SARS-CoV-2 surveillance activities performed by or collaboratively with APHA across pets, livestock or farmed, and wildlife species are completed passively, with the majority of samples being laboratory-confirmed via post-mortem examinations. Additionally, our preliminary results found that surveillance activities currently performed with APHA are based off of current, pre-existing, programmes such as lyssavirus surveillance activities conducted by Bat Conservation trust, and Scanning Surveillance Network. However, most activities and samples collected are livestock/farmed-orientated and hence active surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 is limited in pets and wildlife in this regard.

Passive surveillance is effective in ensuring continuity and detection of diseases if present in a population (Guberti et al., 2014), and this type of surveillance that is being conducted by the APHA is a key method in monitoring for SARS-CoV-2 in wildlife.

Several initiatives currently present are utilised by APHA, which is a good method of allowing more monitoring to occur. Since work is already being conducted, datasets can be extracted from this and interpreted for continuous, passive surveillance. Less monitoring is performed of minks and other mustelidae compared to other European states, as it is less of an economic importance in the UK.

4 Procedure for data collection

After the initial scoping in the UK concluded, a meeting was scheduled with APHA to discuss if there were any information that may have been inaccessible online that relates to our searches, or if there were any other current ongoing work that may not have been made aware from a stand-alone internet search. This informed the approach with the remaining partners.

For the data collection procedure across EU countries, we focused on terminology synonymic with SARS-CoV-2 and the animal species of interest. These data were used to inform a larger repository of surveillance activities being conducted across member countries of COVRIN developed as part of WP3, Task 3.1.1 <https://zenodo.org/record/5541121#.YcCAWWjP1PY>

To help align our search, and ensure that we were capturing information of interest, we used a list of parameters, which was integrated with the data request from Task 3.1, that sought to answer which institutes are:

- in charge of surveillance steering,
- involved in the design of surveillance protocol,
- involved in data collection,
- involved in laboratory analyses,
- involved in data management and data analysis,
- involved in result dissemination

For Task 3.1, these parameters provide additional information on the process that generated the surveillance data collected in this task.

5 Preliminary Results for European surveillance activities

Information for surveillance activities across the period of April 2020 to December 2021 were collected from European partners. While not all data was available at the time of writing this, we highlight in Appendix B the results for several countries. Data were either partially or fully available for surveillance activities across species of interest (pets, livestock/farmed, and wildlife animals) in the countries examined. Additionally, farmed animal surveillance activities were limited to mink only. We found two main approaches across the chain of surveillance activities under consideration: a centralised national level approach, or a multiple agency approach, and often the surveillance findings were due to a specific research project being completed as part of a larger National level surveillance programme. Institute involvement was also dependant on which municipality the surveillance activity was being conducted in. For those COVRIN members completing a multi-agency approach, we found that commonly, activities relating to pets saw the most agencies involved across those surveillance activities. Lastly, one country reported that all activities were completed at the national level, except dissemination of results, which is the responsibility of Chief Veterinary Officer. From the information available, we observed both passive and active surveillance approaches, depending on the species being monitored, with farm animals generally being actively surveyed, while passive approaches were more common with pets and wildlife, Appendix B. Two reports of SARS-Cov-2 were reported in zoo animals – Hippopotamus and Lion (via passive surveillance). These species categories were not initially captured in the search criteria. Data collection is still ongoing, with active engagement from many partners to provide the required information, which was unfortunately not available yet at the time of writing this report. Additionally, several partners reported that analysis of collected samples was still ongoing, with results expected in the coming months.

References

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- The Bat Conservation Trust, B.C., 2021. COVID-19 and Bats - Bats and disease [WWW Document]. Bat Conservation Trust. URL <https://www.bats.org.uk/about-bats/bats-and-disease/covid-19-and-bats> (accessed 11.30.21).

Appendices

Appendix A. List of search terms used for preliminary surveillance activities data collection of SARS-CoV-2 for each animal component

Components	Search terminology				
Non-species specific terms	COVID	surveillance			APHA
	SARS	CoV-2			APHA
	SARS	CoV2			APHA
	Surveillance emerging threats APHA				
Livestock/farmed	Surveillance	SARS	CoV-2	livestock / farmed	UK
	COVID	livestock / farmed	UK		
Wildlife	Surveillance	SARS	CoV2	wildlife	UK
	COVID	surveillance		wildlife	UK
	SARS	CoV2	surveillance	wildlife	UK
	APHA COVID wildlife				
Pets	Surveillance	SARS	CoV2	pets	UK
	Surveillance	SARS	CoV2	dogs	UK
	COVID				pets
	COVID companion animals				

Appendix B. Detailed list of institute involvement across the chain of surveillance activities that are being considered.

Country	Species	Type of surveillance	Institute					
			in charge of surveillance steering	involved in the design of surveillance protocol	involved in data collection	involved in laboratory analyses	involved in data management and data analysis	involved in result dissemination
Spain	Pets (dog, cat, guinea pig, rabbit)	Research project,	National (INIA-CSIC) Centre for Research in Animal Health (CRESA) VISAVET Health Surveillance Center	National (INIA-CSIC) Centre for Research in Animal Health (CRESA) VISAVET Health Surveillance Center	National (INIA-CSIC) Centre for Research in Animal Health (CRESA) VISAVET Health Surveillance Center	National (INIA-CSIC) Centre for Research in Animal Health (CRESA) VISAVET Health Surveillance Center	National (INIA-CSIC) Centre for Research in Animal Health (CRESA) VISAVET Health Surveillance Center	National (INIA-CSIC) Centre for Research in Animal Health (CRESA) VISAVET Health Surveillance Center
	Farmed (mink)	Active and passive	National Reference Laboratory					
	Wildlife		Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown
Poland	Undefined species		National Veterinary Research Institute	Chief Veterinary Officer				
Latvia	Pets (cat)		Institute of food safety, animal health and environment	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment Latvia University of Life Sciences and	Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment

	(dogs)		Food and Veterinary Service	Technologies Food and Veterinary Service	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment
	Farmed (mink)		Food and Veterinary Service	Food and Veterinary Service	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment
	Wildlife (raccoon dog, ferret)		Food and Veterinary Service	Food and Veterinary Service	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment	Institute of food safety, animal health and environment
Sweden	Farmed (mink)	Active	Swedish Board of Agriculture	National Veterinary Institute	National Veterinary Institute	National Veterinary Institute	National Veterinary Institute	National Veterinary Institute
Belgium	Pets			Sciensano (research institute and the national public health institute)	Sciensano (research institute and the national public health institute)	Sciensano (research institute and the national public health institute)	Sciensano (research institute and the national public health institute)	Sciensano (research institute and the national public health institute)
	Wildlife (weasel)		Bruxelles Environment	Sciensano (research institute and the national public health institute)	Sciensano (research institute and the national public health institute)	Sciensano (research institute and the national public health institute)	Sciensano (research institute and the national public health institute)	Sciensano (research institute and the national public health institute)
Germany	Pets (cat, dog)					National Reference Laboratory LUA Sachsen The Institute for Hygiene and Environment Institute for Food Safety, Veterinary Medicine and the Environment		
France	Wildlife (myotis myotis)				Anses / CPEPESC	Anses	Anses / CPEPESC	Anses / CPEPESC
Norway	Pets	Passive	National Food Safety Authority	Norwegian Veterinary Institute	Norwegian Veterinary Institute	Norwegian Veterinary Institute	Norwegian Veterinary Institute	National Food Safety Authority
	Farmed (mink)	Active	National Food Safety Authority	Norwegian Veterinary Institute	Norwegian Veterinary Institute	Norwegian Veterinary Institute	Norwegian Veterinary Institute	National Food Safety Authority
	Wildlife	Passive	National Food Safety Authority	Norwegian Veterinary Institute	Norwegian Veterinary Institute	Norwegian Veterinary Institute	Norwegian Veterinary Institute	National Food Safety Authority